

24 **Main Text:**

25 Earthquake prediction was considered an attainable goal in the early 1970s, based on
26 laboratory and seismic observations showing complementary variations in elastic wave speed
27 prior to rock failure and earthquakes¹. While the excitement attendant with these predictions
28 waned unfulfilled in the following decades, recent works provide accumulating evidence for
29 changes in elastic wave speed associated with a range of fault slip behaviors, including
30 earthquakes^{4,5}, slow fault slip⁶, landslides⁷, and laboratory stick-slip failure events^{2,3}. For the
31 most part, these data document changes during and after failure, although in a few cases
32 premonitory changes are known⁴.

33 The detection and characterization of the physical processes during earthquake
34 nucleation^{8,9} via remote acoustic techniques could provide fundamental insights into the fault
35 weakening mechanisms that precede failure. Laboratory studies have related variations in
36 seismic velocities to the magnitude of applied stress via the existence of networks of microcracks
37 that alter the elastic properties of rocks¹⁰. Moreover, it has been shown that acoustic
38 transmissivity of faults is intimately related with the evolution of shear strength via the load-
39 bearing population of asperity contacts^{2,11}, and laboratory studies show clear precursors to
40 earthquake-like, frictional failure. However, the question of whether such changes in elastic
41 properties can be imaged in the vicinity of earthquake fault and used to forecast failure remains
42 unanswered.

43 Tectonic faults accommodate plate motion via a spectrum of slip behaviors ranging from
44 steady aseismic creep, at mm/yr, to quasi-dynamic transients such as slow earthquakes, with fault
45 slip velocities of $\sim 10^{-7}$ - 10^{-3} m/s, and dynamic rupture with slip velocities of ≥ 1 m/s during
46 powerful earthquakes^{12,13}. The wide range of environments within which these behaviors have

47 been documented¹²⁻¹⁷ and the observation that large earthquakes are often preceded by slow
48 slip^{16,18,19} suggest commonalities in the physical mechanisms of slow and fast rupture. Yet, we
49 neither know if a given fault patch can host both slow slip and dynamic rupture²⁰, nor do we
50 understand the physical properties that dictate rupture speed for slow earthquakes.

51 Here, we use measurements of P-wave velocity linked with mechanical data to illuminate
52 the physical processes that dictate fault weakening and slick-slip frictional failure. We evaluate
53 changes in elastic wave speed during the seismic cycle of slow and fast slip events and find clear
54 precursors to failure that extend across the whole spectrum of slip behaviors.

55 The mechanics of frictional stick-slip can be evaluated for a 1-D fault obeying rate-and-
56 state friction²¹ by considering the elastic stiffness around the fault, k , and the fault frictional
57 properties, which can be written in terms of a critical rheologic stiffness, k_c (see methods). In this
58 context, the ratio $K=k/k_c$ describes the stability boundary between stable, $K>1$, and unstable,
59 $K<1$, behavior. Numerical studies²¹ and limited laboratory data²²⁻²⁴ suggest that the transition
60 from stable to unstable behavior involves a region of oscillatory, quasi-dynamic sliding, near
61 $K=1$. However, the implications of this region for tectonic faulting have not been explored.

62 We report on laboratory experiments designed to investigate the spectrum of fault slip
63 modes from stable creep, slow-slip to fast stick-slip (see methods). We observe a spectrum of
64 slip behaviors as a function of K (ref. 21,23,24) (Figs. 1, Supplementary 1,2). Our experiments
65 document an initial stage of stable sliding, followed by a spontaneous evolution to oscillatory
66 stick-slip and creep-slip behavior with accumulated strain (Fig. 1a and Supplementary 1). We
67 systematically vary K and document a transition from fast, dynamic stick-slip, accompanied by
68 audible energy radiation, to silent slow-slip events (Figs. Supplementary 1,2). For each event we
69 measured the loading stiffness k , peak slip velocity, and stress drop duration (Fig. 1). Slow slip

70 events show peak slip velocity of $\leq 100 \mu\text{m/s}$ resulting in small stress drop events lasting up to 1-
71 2 seconds (Fig. 1). At lower stiffness ($K \sim 0.6$), dynamic stick-slip instabilities occurred with a
72 larger stress drop ($\geq 1 \text{ MPa}$), higher slip velocity ($\geq 2 \text{ mm/s}$) and shorter slip duration ($\leq 0.2 \text{ s}$).
73 The strong negative correlation between stress drop and event duration is consistent with
74 observations from tectonic faults, where slow earthquakes have systematically lower stress drop
75 than regular earthquakes¹².

76 The laboratory slip events exhibit a range of slip velocities that mimic those observed in
77 nature^{13,19}, with peak slip velocities during slow slip events of $\sim 100 \mu\text{m/s}$ and much higher slip
78 rates for fast stick-slip events. We note that our laboratory work focused on the slow end of the
79 spectrum, and did not fully explore faster stick-slip velocities ($\geq 1 \text{ m/s}$) appropriate for regular
80 earthquakes, resulting in a smaller range of slip velocities than that observed in nature.

81 Near the stability boundary, at $K \sim 1$, we observe complex behavior including period
82 doubling and long-period modulation of the stress drop, consistent with theory²¹ (Fig.
83 Supplementary 2). In this framework, the high slip velocity and large stress drop events represent
84 laboratory analogues for regular earthquakes²⁵, whereas the slow, long duration, and small stress
85 drop events are like slow earthquakes.

86 To shed light on the microphysical processes during slow- and fast- stick-slip events, we
87 measured P-wave velocity (V_p), from the P-coda, throughout stick-slip cycles (Fig. 1a inset and
88 method). Wave speed evolves systematically as the fault approaches failure, characterized by an
89 initial increase during elastic loading, followed by a plateau, and a decrease prior to failure (Figs.
90 2 and 3). The reduction in P-wave velocity during stick-slip events is coincident with layer
91 compaction, indicating that wave speed is more sensitive to grain contact stiffness and
92 coordination number than bulk layer density.

93 The combination of frictional properties and acoustic data provide a comprehensive view
94 of fault strength evolution during the seismic cycle (Fig. 3). We find that both slow and fast
95 stick-slip events can be divided into three distinct phases: (I) inter-seismic, described by linear
96 elastic loading; (II) pre-seismic, which begins at the onset of inelastic deformation; and (III) co-
97 seismic, defined by rapid slip acceleration and measured from the peak stress to the residual
98 shear stress after failure. The co-seismic phase can be further divided into a preparatory stage,
99 where the shear stress decreases slowly and fault motion accelerates (IIIa) followed by a failure
100 stage, where dynamic stress drop occurs (IIIb) (Fig. 3a, b). To the best of our knowledge, these
101 are the first observations of elastic wave speed precursors to failure for the complete spectrum of
102 fast to slow slip events (Fig. 3).

103 For both slow and fast slip events, the inter-seismic phase is associated with elastic
104 loading, near zero fault sliding velocity, and increasing V_p (Fig. 3). In this phase the fault is
105 considered locked and the increase in V_p represents contact aging and particle interlocking,
106 consistent with laboratory³ and seismological observations along natural faults^{26,27} (Fig. 4).

107 In the pre-seismic phase (II), creep begins to accelerate and deformation is inelastic.
108 Acceleration in slip velocity coincides with maximum V_p , which generally plateaus during phase
109 II (Fig. 3c, d). For fast stick-slip events, the fault slip velocity is still nearly zero in phase II.
110 Shear stress decreases slowly at the beginning of phase III (Fig. 3) and in this preparatory stage
111 of failure (phase IIIa) accelerated creep coincides with a reduction in V_p of $\sim 1\%$, which is
112 comparable although larger to seismic observations prior to earthquake failure (Fig. 4). During
113 phase IIIb we observe an abrupt increase in slip velocity followed immediately by a rapid stress
114 drop. The maximum slip velocity is attained during phase IIIb, as expected for dynamic rupture.

115 The P-wave velocity shows a marked decrease of ~2-3% coinciding with abrupt acceleration and
116 stress drop (Fig. 3).

117 Our data show that accelerated creep marks the onset of non-linear elastic deformation
118 (i.e. phase II in Fig. 3a, b) and a peak in V_p . This transition is not attendant with macroscopic
119 layer dilation (Fig. 2). Fault creep and the reduction in V_p indicate that asperity contacts within
120 the fault zone begin to fail prior to macroscopic frictional sliding. The onset of creep is likely
121 accommodated by grain boundary sliding, particle rolling, and microcracking, which lead to
122 reduction of elastic wave speed prior to failure. Note that the onset of wave speed reduction and
123 creep occur at similar stages of the loading cycle for slow and fast failure events (Fig. 3),
124 suggesting that the microphysical processes of fault weakening may share key features for slow
125 and fast earthquake rupture (Fig. 4).

126 Our data indicate that earthquake nucleation and slip is controlled by the interaction
127 between fault frictional rheology and local elastic properties of the fault zone and wall rock.
128 Previous works suggest that the major factors dictating the mode of fault slip are frictional
129 properties, effective normal stress, and elastic stiffness of the fault zone^{14,15,28-30}. Fault zone
130 width and maturity may also play a role because they affect friction constitutive parameters, and
131 elastic stiffness (Fig. Supplementary 3). Our observations suggest that the stiffness ratio K
132 incorporates the key parameters for slip stability as applied to tectonic faults and may provide a
133 general mechanism for the spectrum of tectonic fault slip behaviors²⁴, possibly acting in concert
134 with dilatancy hardening or other mechanisms to limit rupture speed^{3,28-30}. The systematic
135 relationship that we observe between shear stress, fault slip rate and V_p during the seismic cycle
136 for slow and fast slip events suggests commonalities in the nucleation and rupture processes for
137 the observed spectrum of slip behaviors²⁰. These data together with existing field observations⁴

138 suggest that seismic velocity precursors may occur during the preparatory phase preceding
139 earthquakes, even if only within a limited region.

140 To address the question of how our data may apply to tectonic faults, we note that active
141 seismic surveys and analysis of ambient seismic noise have documented systematic changes in
142 elastic wave speed associated with earthquakes^{4-6,27}. In both the laboratory and nature, seismic
143 wave speed decreases during coseismic slip and increases during the interseismic period (Fig. 4).
144 In nature, the most obvious changes occur after earthquake rupture; wave speed drops abruptly
145 coseismically and then increases with log-time, consistent with fault re-strengthening due to
146 healing mechanisms^{26,27}. A coseismic reduction in wave speed has been documented for a
147 number of major earthquakes ($M>6$)⁵. Additionally, in special cases where high resolution
148 monitoring was carried out, precursory changes in seismic wave speed have been observed prior
149 to a M3 earthquake⁴ (Fig 4c). Similar observations of velocity reduction have been reported
150 during slow earthquakes⁶, where the maximum seismic velocity perturbation was observed at the
151 time of maximum strain change (Fig. 4d). Although fault dimensions and wave frequencies in
152 natural and laboratory studies differ, and a more comprehensive discussion is required, the
153 similarities between natural observations and our results, suggest the applicability of our findings
154 to natural faults (Fig. 4).

155 Our data show that the state of stress on a fault can be monitored by P-wave velocity
156 changes during the seismic cycle. In particular, we document fault creep and a reduction in V_p
157 during a preparatory phase (IIIa) preceding failure (IIIb). Recent works show that large
158 earthquakes are often preceded by slow slip during a preparatory phase^{16,18}, which is consistent
159 with our observations. In summary, our data illuminate: 1) key connections in the underlying

160 physics of slow and fast earthquake rupture nucleation, and 2) precursory changes in seismic
161 velocity that may be a promising avenue for the detection of earthquake precursors.

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225 contacting the corresponding author.

226 **Acknowledgments:** We thank Massimo Cocco, Paul Johnson, John Leeman and Demian Saffer
227 for discussion regarding this work. We also thank Piergiorgio Scarlato for support at the INGV
228 HP-HT laboratory. This research was supported by ERC grant Nr. 259256 GLASS to CC,
229 visiting professor 2015 SAPIENZA grant and grants NSF-EAR1520760 and DE- EE0006762 to
230 CM, and European Union Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under the Marie
231 Sklodowska-Curie No. 656676 FEAT to MMS.

232 **Author Contributions:** All the authors contributed to the experimental design, data analysis and
233 writing. M.M. Scuderi, C. Marone and C. Collettini conducted experiments and data analysis, E.
234 Tinti and M.M. Scuderi developed the model for acoustic wave propagation and performed
235 waveforms analysis, G. Di Stefano and M.M. Scuderi developed the waveforms recording
236 system and synchronization.

237 **Competing Financial Interests:** The authors declare no competing financial interests.

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239 **Figure Legends:**

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241 **Figure 1. The spectrum of fault slip behaviour along experimental faults.** (a) Representative
242 experiment at $\sigma_n=15$ MPa. Left inset shows the double direct shear configuration. Right inset
243 shows details for a slow-slip event (red) with associated recorded waveforms (grey) and the
244 correspondent variations in flight time (top). The stiffness ratio, K , controls the transition from
245 slow to fast stick-slip as mapped in the stability phase diagram (b), the peak slip velocity (c), and
246 the slip event duration (d). Inset in panel (c) shows the linear fit (red dashed line) to the shear
247 stress curves (black) used to obtain k , and slip velocity (grey). Inset in panel (d) shows a failure
248 event and the duration of the stress drop.

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250 **Figure 2. Mechanical and P-wave velocity measurements during slow-slip (top) and fast-**
251 **slip cycles (lower curves).** Data showing the evolution of shear stress (black), layer thickness
252 (blue) and changes in P-wave velocity (V_p) (red) during slow (top set of curves) and fast (lower
253 curves) stick-slip events. Inset shows a typical waveform with the P-wave arrival and the P-coda
254 used to calculate V_p (see Fig. Supplementary 4 and methods for additional details). Note the
255 consistency in the V_p evolution during the slow and fast stick-slip cycles, mimicking the
256 evolution of shear stress.

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258 **Figure 3. Comparison between slow slip and fast stick-slip cycles.** Details of slow (left
259 column) and fast (right column) stick-slip events. (a, b) Representative slip events taken at shear
260 displacement of 25 mm, and (c, d, e, f) at displacement of 30 mm. The evolution of shear stress
261 (black), slip velocity (blue) and P-wave velocity (red) is shown as a function of: (a, b) fault slip
262 and (c, d, e, f) time. The grey shaded boxes indicate the three phases of the seismic cycle: (I)
263 inter-seismic, (II) pre-seismic and (III) co-seismic, as described in the text.

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265 **Figure 4. Comparison between laboratory and natural variation in seismic velocity.** Seismic
266 velocity changes during the earthquake cycle for fast (a) and slow (b) laboratory earthquakes and
267 fault slip events in nature ranging from typical earthquakes (c and e) to slow-slip events (d).
268 Grey shaded bands in (b) and (d) represent slow-slip events in the lab and in nature.

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Figure 3. Comparison between slow slip and fast stick-slip cycles. Details of slow (left column) and fast (right column) stick-slip events. (a, b) Representative slip events taken at shear displacement of 25 mm, and (c, d, e, f) at displacement of 30 mm. The evolution of shear stress (black), slip velocity (blue) and P-wave velocity (red) is shown as a function of: (a, b) fault slip and (c, d, e, f) time. The grey shaded boxes indicate the three phases of the seismic cycle: (I) inter-seismic, (II) pre-seismic and (III) co-seismic, as described in the text.

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Figure 4. Comparison between laboratory and natural variation in seismic velocity. Seismic velocity changes during the earthquake cycle for fast (a) and slow (b) laboratory earthquakes and fault slip events in nature ranging from typical earthquakes (c and e) to slow-slip events (d). Grey shaded bands in (b) and (d) represent slow-slip events in the lab and in nature.

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307 **Methods:**

308 Friction experiments

309 All experiments were performed in a double direct shear configuration using a biaxial
310 loading frame (Brittle Rock deformAtion Versatile Apparatus, BRAVA, at HP-HT laboratory
311 INGV, Rome)³¹. Two fast-acting servo-hydraulic rams are used to apply horizontal and vertical
312 load. The applied load was measured via strain gauge load cells (accuracy $\pm 0.03\text{kN}$) positioned
313 at the extremity of the rams in contact with the sample assembly. Horizontal and vertical
314 displacements were measured by Linear Variable Displacement Transformers (LVDTs), with an
315 accuracy of $\pm 0.1\mu\text{m}$, referenced at the load frame and the upper side of the ram. Additionally,
316 two Direct Current Displacement Transducers (DCDTs), with an accuracy of $\pm 0.1\mu\text{m}$, were
317 mounted directly on the sample assembly (Fig. 1a inset). The first DCDT was positioned in the
318 horizontal direction and used to accurately resolve details of sample compaction/dilation,
319 avoiding unlikely artifacts from the remote measurement of the LVDT positioned on the ram.
320 The second DCDT was mounted at the top of the shearing block and referenced at the end-
321 platen, to measure the true fault slip.

322 The sample assembly consisted of two layers of simulated fault gouge sandwiched
323 between three steel forcing blocks equipped with grooves (0.8 mm high and 2 mm spacing) to
324 couple the gouge and eliminate boundary shear. We used granular quartz powder as simulated
325 fault gouge. The powder is (Min-U-Sil 40, U.S. Silica Co.), 99.5% SiO_2 with traces of metal
326 oxides and a median grain diameter of $10.5\mu\text{m}$. We chose granular quartz because it is a
327 common mineral in natural fault gouge and a well studied material with reproducible frictional
328 behavior. Gouge layers were prepared using leveling gigs to achieve a constant initial layer

329 thickness of 3 mm and a nominal frictional contact area of 5 x 5 cm. All experiments were
330 performed at room temperature and under 100% relative humidity.

331 We conducted two types of experiments. (1) Stiff experiments were used to determine
332 rate- and state-friction parameters ($a-b$) and D_c to directly calculate k_c (Fig. Supplementary 3 and
333 Table Supplementary 1). In these experiments a normal load of 15 or 25 MPa was applied and
334 maintained constant throughout the experiment via a force-feedback servo control. Gouge layers
335 were allowed to compact under load prior to shear to allow compaction and densification. Shear
336 was induced by driving the vertical ram at constant displacement rate of 10 $\mu\text{m/s}$ measured at the
337 top of the central forcing block in the double direct shear arrangement (Fig. 1a inset). Once a
338 steady state coefficient of friction was achieved (usually after 5 mm of shear) a series of velocity
339 steps, from 10 – 1 – 3 to 10 $\mu\text{m/s}$ were performed. The sequence was repeated throughout these
340 experiments until a shear displacement of ~ 25 mm was achieved. (2) Experiments with lower
341 shear stiffness were performed by placing a spring ($k = 0.0296264$ MPa/ μm , for our sample size)
342 in series between the vertical ram and the central forcing block. In these experiments the normal
343 load was varied from 13 to 25 MPa and the shear velocity was maintained constant (10 $\mu\text{m/s}$)
344 throughout the experiments until a displacement of ~ 30 mm was achieved.

345 In the context of frictional stability²¹, when sliding velocity is still slow, the threshold
346 between stable sliding and stick-slip is defined by the interaction between the surrounding
347 stiffness, k , and a rheologic critical stiffness k_c :

$$348 \quad k < k_c = \frac{(\sigma_n - P_f)(b-a)}{D_c} \quad (1)$$

349 where σ_n is the normal stress, P_f is the pore fluid pressure, ($b-a$) is the friction rate parameter,
350 and D_c is the critical slip distance. Equation 1 represents simplified elastic and frictional
351 conditions, but it is consistent with more complex models of earthquake nucleation²⁸⁻³⁰ and

352 applicable to the slow, early stages of slip nucleation. If the stiffness of the loading system (k) is
353 less than the critical stiffness (i.e. $k < k_c$), instability occurs because the fault weakening rate,
354 given by k_c , exceeds the rate of elastic unloading, resulting in a force imbalance and acceleration.
355 For stiffer systems, in which elastic unloading outpaces frictional weakening, $k > k_c$, sliding is
356 stable.

357 To investigate the full spectrum of frictional slip behaviors, we altered the effective
358 stiffness of the loading system, $k' [\mu\text{m}^{-1}] = k/\sigma_n$, to the desired values (i.e. to be greater, less or
359 equal to k_c) (Eq. 1). To determine the rate- and state-friction parameters, ($a-b$) and D_c , from the
360 stiff experiments (Fig. Supplementary 3b, c), we modeled each velocity step using an iterative
361 singular value decomposition technique, which solves the rate- and state-friction equations using
362 the Ruina evolution law coupled with the elastic interaction of the testing machine³²⁻³⁴ (Fig.
363 Supplementary 3a). Direct calculation of k_c yields a threshold value of $8 \times 10^{-4} [\mu\text{m}^{-1}]$ (Fig.
364 Supplementary 3d). For experiments with reduced stiffness, k is given by the summation, in
365 series, of the stiffness of the loading apparatus and the spring. We further altered the effective
366 stiffness by varying the normal stress (Table Supplementary 1). We measured k_{ev} (representing
367 the stiffness of the loading system and gouge layers) from the linear elastic portion of each stick-
368 slip event using a least-square linear fit to the friction vs. displacement curves. We find that k_{ev}
369 increases as normal load is decreased and at the transition between unstable to stable behavior
370 we obtain values of $k_{ev} \sim 0.001 [\mu\text{m}^{-1}]$ (Fig. Supplementary 3e). Comparing our direct ($k_c = 8 \times 10^{-4}$
371 $[\mu\text{m}^{-1}]$) and empirical ($k_{ev} = 0.001 [\mu\text{m}^{-1}]$) measurements of k_c we note that the values are quite
372 similar. The stiffness ratio K reported in Figure 1b is then calculated as the ratio between the k_{ev}
373 measured for each stick-slip cycle and an averaged $k_c = 0.0009 [\mu\text{m}^{-1}]$.

374 Ultrasonic Measurements

375 Elastic properties were measured with two, 20-mm diameter, 2-mm thick, barium-titanate
376 P-type Piezoelectric transducers (PZT), with a central frequency of 1MHz (PI Sensor PIC255).
377 PZTs were embedded into cavities within each of the side forcing blocks and positioned at a
378 distance of 13.5 mm from the fault gouge boundary (Fig. 1a inset and Supplementary 4a). One
379 PZT (Transmitter) is excited by a high voltage (900V) and very short ($\sim 0.8 \mu\text{s}$) pulse at a
380 repetition rate between 50 and 100Hz, using a custom-made pulse generator. Each waveform
381 was received by the PZT (Receiver) at the opposite side of the sample assembly after passing
382 through the gouge layers and forcing blocks. We recorded the output signal with an eight
383 channel, 14-bit, fast AD converter (ADLink PXIe-9848) at sampling rates up to 100MHz. For
384 these experiments we configured the board for finite acquisition at 50MHz with a capture
385 duration of $200 \mu\text{s}$ (10000 points per signal). Each waveform is synchronized in real-time during
386 the experiment with the mechanical data.

387 To calculate P-wave velocity we used cross correlation to pick P-wave first arrival as
388 well as P-coda. The cross-correlation procedure followed standard techniques where, for a time
389 interval of the experiment, a specific pattern of a master waveform is compared to other
390 seismograms to identify a time-shift in the selected wave pattern (Fig. 1a inset). One benefit of
391 cross correlation is that it can offer up to a tenfold increase in temporal resolution compared to
392 the data sampling rate. Thus, we subsampled each master wave and seismogram with a 50x
393 spline fit. The arrival time of a wave pattern is called “*flight time*” and is defined as the time
394 required to go from the source to the receiver. To obtain the absolute P-wave velocity for our
395 experiments, we performed calibration experiments where we loaded the empty assembly (side +
396 central steel blocks) at normal loads between 5 and 25 MPa. This calibration returned an average
397 flight time $t_0 = 13.6 \mu\text{s}$ which correspond to a P-wave velocity of $5421.2 \pm 5.2 \text{ m/s}$.

398 For our experiments with gouge layers, the P-wave velocity can be computed as:

$$399 \quad v_p(t) = \frac{2 \cdot h(t)}{T(t) - t_0} \quad (2)$$

400 where $h(t)$ is the thickness of one gouge layer, $T(t)$ is the flight time of the P-wave first arrival
401 and t_0 is the calibration time (which is constant all over the experiments) (Fig. Supplementary 4
402 data coded in green). Generally, the first arrival was quite noisy and for this reason we focused
403 on the P-wave coda, consistent with previous work³.

404 We developed a new approach to retrieve the absolute value of the P-wave velocity by
405 using coda waves (Fig. Supplementary 4). We consider a simplified propagation model with
406 linear ray path, following Snell's theory, with rays that reflect at the interfaces of our sample
407 assembly with an incidence angle equal to zero (Fig. Supplementary 4a red and blue paths). In
408 this context the definition of "coda waves" correspond to all the excitations due to the
409 summation of constructive or destructive effects of reflected or transmitted rays that are recorded
410 after the first arrival. We modified Eq. 2 as follow:

$$411 \quad v_p(t) = \frac{(N_{g1} + N_{g2}) \cdot h(t)}{T(t) - [(N_{e1} + N_{e2}) \cdot t_e + N_c \cdot t_c]} \quad (3)$$

412 where $T(t)$ is the P-coda flight time, t_e and t_c are the P-wave flight times along the two side
413 blocks and the central block respectively, calculated from the calibration; the coefficients N_{g1}, N_{g2}
414 represent the number of reflections within the gouge layers; N_{e1}, N_{e2}, N_c represent the number of
415 reflections within the side steel forcing blocks and the central forcing block respectively; and $h(t)$
416 is the layer thickness. Eq. 3 reduces to Eq. 2 when the first arrival is considered. In Figure
417 Supplementary 4 we show an example of the P-wave velocity calculated using the first arrival
418 (green), and two P-codas (red and blue). Note that by using the P-coda we sensibly decrease the
419 noise in the data without changing the absolute P-wave velocity (compare green and blue
420 curves).

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422 **References:**

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433 **Supplementary Materials:**
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437 **Figure Supplementary 1.** Records of shear stress as a function of shear strain for representative
438 experiments at three normal stresses, σ_n , and a constant shearing rate of $10\mu\text{m/s}$. In each case,
439 shear is initially stable and transitions to unstable stick-slip spontaneously. Lower right inset
440 shows detail of slip events (solid line is stress) and the corresponding fault slip (dashed lines)
441 across the transition from slow to fast stick-slip.
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446 **Figure Supplementary 2.** Friction records for a series of experiments performed at different
 447 normal stresses to span the transition from fast stick-slip to stable sliding. As the stiffness ratio
 448 increases we document a net decrease in stress (friction) drop, an increase in stress drop duration
 449 and an increase in the frequency of the events. As the stability threshold is approached (i.e. $K \sim$
 450 1) period doubling ($\sigma_n = 15$ MPa) and amplitude modulation of stress drop ($\sigma_n = 14$ MPa) arise,
 451 reflecting chaotic behavior. When $K > 1$ we observe stable shear. Note that the transition from
 452 fast stick-slip to steady sliding takes place in a very narrow range of normal stresses. All data are
 453 reported in terms of friction coefficient ($\mu = \tau/\sigma_n$) and have been offset for clarity.
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457 **Figure Supplementary 3.** Experimental data and modeling procedure used to obtain the rate-
 458 and state- friction parameters. (a) Representative data for a velocity step from 10 to 1 $\mu\text{m/s}$. The
 459 evolution of frictional strength is shown as a function of shear displacement (black). Results of
 460 the model inversion are shown in red superimposed on the raw data. (b) The friction rate
 461 parameter $(a-b)$ shows a transition from velocity strengthening to velocity weakening as shear
 462 displacement increases. (c) The critical slip distance (D_c) decreases with increasing
 463 displacement. (d) The resulting critical rheologic stiffness, k_c , increases as a function of
 464 displacement. (e) Evolution of the stiffness computed for each slip event (k) in three experiments
 465 (Table Supplementary 1) as a function of shear displacement. Grey box indicate the interval of
 466 the data we used in Figure 1a, b.
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Figure Supplementary 4. (a) Schematic representation of the double direct shear configuration, showing the propagation model with elastic wave ray paths of the direct wave (green) and two reflected waveforms (red and blue). (b) Typical master waveform taken at the beginning of a slow slip event (red dot in panel d). (c) Zoom of the master waveform (red box in b) indicating the P-wave arrival and the P-wave coda. Two patterns corresponding to the reflections schemes indicated in (a) are shown. (d) Evolution of time of flight, P-wave velocity and change in P-wave velocity (%) for two slow slip events (upper panel), obtained from the cross-correlation of the P-wave arrival (green) and P-wave coda (red and blue).

Experiment Number	Normal Stress (MPa)	Velocity ($\mu\text{m/s}$)	Spring Constant (MPa/ μm)	RH (%)	Comments
i416	15	Run in 10 v.steps 1-3-10	NO	100	Velocity Steps
i433	25	Run in 10 v.steps 1-3-10	NO	100	Velocity Steps
i266	13	10	0.0296264	100	Stable Sliding
i268	13.5	10	0.0296264	100	Stable Sliding
i267	14	10	0.0296264	100	Slow-Slip
i371	15	10	0.0296264	100	Slow-Slip
i390	15	10	0.0296264	100	Slow-Slip
i420	15	10	0.0296264	100	Slow-Slip
i363	20	10	0.0296264	100	Intermediate
i373	20	10	0.0296264	100	Intermediate
i418	20	10	0.0296264	100	Intermediate
i372	25	10	0.0296264	100	Audible Stick-Slip
i391	25	10	0.0296264	100	Audible Stick-Slip
i415	25	10	0.0296264	100	Audible Stick-Slip
i417	25	10	0.0296264	100	Audible Stick-Slip
i433	25	10	0.0296264	100	Audible Stick-Slip

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Table Supplementary 1. Summary of experiments and boundary conditions. All tests were conducted under 100% relative humidity (RH) to ensure experimental reproducibility.